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PIN4 has functions in homeostasis.

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PIN4 functions in isomerization of peptidyl-prolyl bonds.

Citations

1. Jiang, B. and Pei, D., 2015. A selective, cell-permeable nonphosphorylated bicyclic peptidyl inhibitor against peptidyl-prolyl isomerase Pin1. *Journal of medicinal chemistry*, 58(15), pp.6306-6312.